

Application generated by artificial intelligence

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Abstract

The article focuses on generating the code of a simple application for finding the current temperature according to a specified city in the Slovak Republic. The code is fully generated using artificial intelligence tools, namely Gemini, Grok, ChatGPT and DeepSeek chatbots. It is assumed that in the near future these tools could largely take over programming/code generation and thus significantly reduce the need for human programmers. The aim of our article is to examine the current state of the art in this field and whether three different chatbots can generate, without additional assistance, a separate functional code for an application that has only one purpose, namely finding the weather from the shmu.sk domain. In individual chapters, we describe the creation of a test environment and the deployment of the code generated by artificial intelligence and compare it with the deployment of the authors' code.

Keywords

artificial intelligence, Python, automation, programming

1 Introduction

In recent years, there has been significant progress in the field of artificial intelligence, with machine learning and deep learning enabling increasingly complex tasks to be solved. Nevertheless, there remain areas where human programming demonstrates higher efficiency, especially in cases requiring high interpretability, adaptation to non-standard scenarios, or ethical constraints. The aim of our article is a simple comparison between AI-based programming and traditional human approaches in solving a specialized task: creating an application to retrieve the current temperature from the Slovak Hydrometeorological Institute website (www.shmu.sk). The paper is best understood as an exploratory case study rather than a comprehensive evaluation of AI-generated programming.

2 Environment Setup

We selected Linux Ubuntu 22.04 as the primary operating system for the experiments (Petersen, 2025). The environment was deployed on Google Cloud using a virtual machine with hardware parameters including four CPUs (AuthenticAMD, AMD EPYC 7B12) and 4 GB of RAM. Although these specifications are modest, they are sufficient for the experiment.

After installing the OS, we set up Python (version 3.10.12) and the Pip package manager (version 22.0.2). We also installed recommended libraries necessary for running all scripts (Lubanovic, 2019).

Our goal was to:

- Generate Python code using AI tools
- Test the generated code in practical deployment

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```

import requests from bs4 import BeautifulSoup

def ziskaj_teplotu(mesto): # Mapovanie názvu mesta na URL parameter mesta = {
'bratislava': 'http://www.shmu.sk/sk/?page=1&id=meteo_mestske&station=BA',
'kosice': 'http://www.shmu.sk/sk/?page=1&id=meteo_mestske&station=KE', 'zilina':
'http://www.shmu.sk/sk/?page=1&id=meteo_mestske&station=ZA', # pridaj ďalšie
mestá podľa SHMÚ }

mesto_url = mesta.get(mesto.lower())
if not mesto_url:
    print(f"Mesto '{mesto}' nie je podporované.")
    return

response = requests.get(mesto_url)
if response.status_code != 200:
    print("Nepodarilo sa načítať dáta zo SHMÚ.")
    return

soup = BeautifulSoup(response.text, 'html.parser')

# Hľadanie elementu s teplotou - môže sa zmeniť podľa aktuálnej HTML štruktúry
teplota_element = soup.find('td', class_='td_temp') # Pozor: treba overiť
aktuálnu triedu!

if teplota_element:
    print(f"Aktuálna teplota v {mesto.title()}: {teplota_element.text.strip()}
°C")
else:
    print("Teplotu sa nepodarilo nájsť.")

1 #Príklad použitia

mesto = input("Zadaj mesto (napr. Bratislava, Kosice): ") ziskaj_teplotu(mesto)

```

Figure 1. Code generated by chatGPT (version: GPT-4o)

- Implement an experiment using the authors' own code
- Compare and interpret the results

3 Results

Each code was executed three times for verification. The AI-generated codes came from ChatGPT, Gemini, Grok and DeepSeek. The initial prompt was: 'ahoj, vies urobit aplikaciu v pythone, ktora po zadani mesta vypise teplotu v stupnoch C zo stranky shmu.sk?', translated: 'hi, can you make an application in python that, after entering a city, prints the temperature in degrees C from the website shmu.sk?'. Despite being written without diacritics, all chatbots understood the question. However, none of the generated codes returned the correct temperature data from SHMÚ. The authors' own Python code successfully retrieved the temperature using web scraping techniques, while all AI-generated codes failed.

Note: The resulting sample codes may require additional editing in the form of indentation (tabs) to function properly, as they may have been automatically modified by text/graphics software. Result outputs were translated to English language in the codes „result“ sections.

Result 1 - Figure 1

Enter city (e.g. Bratislava, Kosice): Bratislava

```

import requests from bs4 import BeautifulSoup

def
ziskaj_teploty_zo_shmu(url="https://www.shmu.sk/sk/?page=1&id=meteo_apocasiae_sk"
): """ Získa aktuálne teploty zo stránky SHMÚ pomocou web scrapingu.

Args:
    url (str): URL adresa SHMÚ stránky s aktuálnym počasím.

Returns:
    dict: Slovník, kde kľúčom je názov stanice a hodnotou je teplota v °C.
    Vráti prázdny slovník, ak sa dáta nepodarí získať.
    """
teploty = {}
try:
    # Stiahnutie obsahu stránky
    response = requests.get(url, timeout=10) # Nastavenie timeoutu pre prípad,
že stránka neodpovedá
    response.raise_for_status() # Vyvolá HTTPError pre chybné status kódy (4xx,
5xx)

    # Parsovanie HTML obsahu
    soup = BeautifulSoup(response.text, 'html.parser')

    # SHMÚ zvyčajne zobrazuje dáta v tabuľkách.
    # Skúsime nájsť tabuľku s ID 'data-tabulka' alebo triedou, ktorá obsahuje
meteo dáta.
    # Táto časť kódu je najcitlivejšia na zmeny štruktúry SHMÚ stránky.
    tabulka = soup.find('table', {'class': 'dm_tabulka', 'id': 'data-tabulka'})

    if tabulka:
        # Prejdeme cez riadky tabuľky (tr)
        for riadok in tabulka.find_all('tr'):
            # Nájdenie všetkých dátových buniek (td) v riadku
            bunky = riadok.find_all('td')
            if len(bunky) >= 3: # Potrebujeme aspoň 3 bunky (stanica, teplota,
čas/ďalšie info)
                stanica = bunky[0].get_text(strip=True)
                teplota_str = bunky[2].get_text(strip=True) # Teplota je často v
tretom stĺpci

                try:
                    # Pokúsime sa prekonvertovať teplotu na float
                    teplota = float(teplota_str.replace(',', '.').replace(' °C',
''))

                    teploty[stanica] = teplota
                except ValueError:
                    # Ak sa nepodarí prekonvertovať, preskočíme
                    continue
            else:
                print("Chyba: Nenašla sa tabuľka s aktuálnymi dátami na stránke SHMÚ.")

except requests.exceptions.RequestException as e:
    print(f"Chyba pri sťahovaní stránky: {e}")
except Exception as e:
    print(f"Nastala neočakávaná chyba: {e}")

```

Figure 2. Code generated by Gemini (version: 2.5 Flash)

Output: Temperature could not be found.

```

return teploty

if name == "main": aktualne_teploty = ziskaj_teploty_zo_shmu()

    if aktualne_teploty:
        print("Aktuálne teploty zo SHMÚ:")
        for stanica, temp in aktualne_teploty.items():
            print(f"- {stanica}: {temp}°C")
    else:
        print("Nepodarilo sa získať údaje o teplotách zo SHMÚ.")

print("\n---")
print("Pre konkrétne mesto musíte prejsť cez získaný slovník a nájsť
zhodu.")
print("Napríklad pre Bratislavu:")

hladane_mesto = input("Zadajte mesto, pre ktoré chcete nájsť teplotu
(napr. Bratislava): ")
found = False
for stanica, temp in aktualne_teploty.items():
    if hladane_mesto.lower() in stanica.lower():
        print(f"- {stanica}: {temp}°C")
        found = True
if not found:
    print(f"Pre mesto '{hladane_mesto}' sa nenašli žiadne záznamy.")

```

Figure 3. Continuation of Code generated by Gemini (version: 2.5 Flash)

Result 2 - Figure 2 and 3

Enter city (e.g. Bratislava, Kosice): Bratislava

Output: Error: No table with current data found on the SHMÚ website.

Unable to retrieve temperature data from SHMÚ.

For a specific city, you need to go through the retrieved dictionary and find a match. For example, for Bratislava: Enter the city for which you want to find the temperature (e.g. Bratislava): Bratislava No records were found for the city 'Bratislava'.

Result 3 - Figure 4

Enter city name (or 'end' to exit): Bratislava

Output: Temperature data for Bratislava was not found.

Enter city name (or 'end' to exit):

Result 4 - Figure 5

System: Welcome to the application for getting the current temperature from SHMU.sk

Enter the name of the city: Bratislava

Output: Unable to find the table with data.

The following is the authors' code, which is shortened (Fig. 6) and provided only as an example, as the authors are interested in finding out whether artificial intelligence has improved the ability to create code for this type of application so that it is functional. The authors therefore do not want to create a guide for artificial intelligence on how to program the code. If the reader wants to verify the authors' code functionality, it is possible to verify whether the

```

import requests from bs4 import BeautifulSoup import re

def get_temperature(city): # Normalizácia názvu mesta (odstránenie diakritiky
pre URL) city = city.lower().strip() # Nahradzame diakritiku pre jednoduchšie
vyhladavanie diacritics = { 'á': 'a', 'ä': 'a', 'č': 'c', 'ď': 'd', 'é': 'e',
'í': 'i', 'l': 'l', 'ň': 'n', 'ó': 'o', 'ô': 'o', 'r': 'r', 'š': 's', 't': 't',
'ú': 'u', 'ý': 'y', 'ž': 'z' } for char, repl in diacritics.items(): city =
city.replace(char, repl)

# Vytvorenie URL pre vyhľadavanie na SHMÚ
base_url = "https://www.shmu.sk/sk/?page=1&subpage=3&name="
url = base_url + city

try:
    # Odoslanie HTTP požiadavky
    response = requests.get(url, headers={'User-Agent': 'Mozilla/5.0'})
    response.raise_for_status() # Overenie, či požiadavka bola úspešná

    # Parsovanie HTML obsahu
    soup = BeautifulSoup(response.text, 'html.parser')

    # Hľadanie elementu s teplotou (napr. v tabuľke alebo meteograme)
    # SHMÚ zvyčajne zobrazuje teplotu v div s triedou 'actual' alebo podobnej
    temp_element = soup.find('div', class_='actual')
    if temp_element:
        # Extrahovanie textu s teplotou
        temp_text = temp_element.get_text(strip=True)
        # Predpokladáme formát ako "12 °C" alebo "12°C"
        match = re.search(r'(\d+\.\d*)\s*°C', temp_text)
        if match:
            temperature = match.group(1)
            return f"Aktuálna teplota v meste {city.title()} je {temperature}
°C"
        else:
            return f"Teplota pre mesto {city.title()} nebola nájdená."
    else:
        return f"Údaje o teplote pre mesto {city.title()} neboli nájdené."

except requests.exceptions.RequestException as e:
    return f"Chyba pri získavaní údajov: {e}"

def main():
    while True:
        city = input("Zadaj názov mesta (alebo 'koniec' pre ukončenie): ")
        if city.lower() == 'koniec':
            print("Ukončujem program.")
            break
        if not city.strip():
            print("Prosím, zadaj platný názov mesta.")
            continue
        result = get_temperature(city)
        print(result)
if name == "main":
    main()

```

Figure 4. Code generated by Grok (version: Grok 3)

code returns the correct data in real time at the provided link (if SHMÚ did not modify page code in the meantime, then the code snippet works correctly) <http://rsrch.ddns.net/rsrch/shmu/> and compare if the resulting data with the selected one on www.shmu.sk (temperature data in the chosen city, e.g., Bratislava) match.

```

import requests
from bs4 import BeautifulSoup

def get_temperature(city):
    try:
        # URL SHMU s meteorologickými dátami
        url = "https://www.shmu.sk/sk/?page=1&id=meteo_num_alad"

        # Stiahnutie stránky
        response = requests.get(url)
        response.raise_for_status()

        # Spracovanie HTML
        soup = BeautifulSoup(response.text, 'html.parser')

        # Nájdenie tabuľky s údajmi
        table = soup.find('table', {'class': 'border'})
        if not table:
            return "Nepodarilo sa nájsť tabuľku s údajmi."

        # Hľadanie riadku pre zadané mesto
        for row in table.find_all('tr')[1:]: # preskočiť hlavičku
            columns = row.find_all('td')
            if len(columns) >= 2:
                current_city = columns[0].get_text(strip=True)
                if city.lower() in current_city.lower():
                    temperature = columns[1].get_text(strip=True)
                    return f"Aktuálna teplota v {current_city}: {temperature}°C"

        return f"Mesto '{city}' sa nenašlo v zozname."

    except requests.RequestException as e:
        return f"Chyba pri pripájaní k SHMU: {e}"
    except Exception as e:
        return f"Vyskytla sa chyba: {e}"

# Hlavná časť programu
if __name__ == "__main__":
    print("Vitajte v aplikácii pre získanie aktuálnej teploty zo SHMU.sk")
    city = input("Zadajte názov mesta: ")
    result = get_temperature(city)
    print(result)

```

Figure 5. Code generated by DeepSeek (version: DeepSeek-V3)

Result 5 - Figure 6

Enter city (default=Bratislava):

Output: The temperature for the city of Bratislava is 22.5 °C

From the above examples, we can see that none of the used chatbots was able to generate the required code returning the correct result, although the data is located on the main page www.shmu.sk and there is no need to go deeper into the code of the subpages. The author prepared a code using the Python language, which, like the artificial intelligence codes, downloaded the initial website shmu.sk to the local computer and then, by analyzing the obtained data, determined the relevant temperature in a given city. This experiment shows that artificial intelligence can solve various complex tasks when many existing solutions are implemented, from which it learns, but sometimes even a banal task (as in this article) leads to failure for all the studied chatbots.

```
import requests
from bs4 import BeautifulSoup
import csv
def scrape_page(soup, quotes):
    cdata = soup.find(string=re.compile("CDATA"))
    import string
    cdata2=cdata.split(",")
    global m
    m = "Bratislava"
    m = input("Zadaj mesto (default=%s): " % m) or m
    found=False
    for mesto in cdata2:
        if m.capitalize() in mesto:
            quotes.append(mesto)
            found=True
            break
    if not found:
        print("Mesto nenajdene")
```

Figure 6. A brief look at the part of authors' code

4 Discussion

The chatbot versions were tested in the period June-July 2025, and therefore in the future it would be appropriate to repeat the test for newer versions of chatbots. It is assumed that in the upcoming years artificial intelligence will advance to such a level that this simple test will be successfully passed, as well as more complex implementations of other applications. The test on the SHMÚ website with our version of the code was carried out in the same period as for the artificial intelligence tools, namely in the months of June-July 2025. Our code may not work in future tests, as it is based on the so-called web scraping technology (Clark, 2025), where it is important to browse the structures of the main SHMÚ website. If these structures change, for example, the appearance of the main page changes significantly, the application may stop working completely. This approach (web scraping) is purely experimental and intended only for research purposes, as it may raise questions about the legality of the data obtained in this way.

5 Conclusion

In the article, we described the procedure of how we designed an experiment to obtain relevant data from the main page of the SHMÚ using the web scraping technology implemented by the authors of the article and then tested applications that generated three different chatbots based on the LLM (Large Language Model) technology, which were supposed to program the application based on the specified parameters (Campeato, 2024). The experiment showed that the current versions of the chatbots could not handle this task and none of them could provide the required data from the SHMÚ website.

Resources

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